

Physiological Responses to Musical Stimuli - an Initial Investigation

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Abstract

This work-in-progress paper presents findings from a pilot study ($N = 30$), conducted as part of the Horizon Europe AMPLIFY project, investigating physiological responses to music. Participants listened to two counterbalanced musical excerpts while heart rate, electrodermal activity (EDA) and skin temperature were recorded via EmotiBit™ wearable sensors. Of 489 statistically significant individual deviations from baseline (Bonferroni-corrected Mann-Whitney U), 33 were shared across multiple participants. To check whether these occurred at the same instant, temporal analysis of the shared deviations identified 82 different episodes in which multiple participants deviated simultaneously. Comparing audio features during these episodes to the remainder of each musical excerpt yielded 27 Bonferroni-significant associations (Cohen's d up to 1.62). Broadband EDA and skin conductance response frequency emerged as the most responsive physiological measures, showing strong correlations with spectral brightness and timbral features of the musical passages.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing**; • **Sound and music computing**; • **Social and professional topics**; • **User characteristics**;

ACM Reference Format:

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1 Introduction

'Concertos para Bebés' [1] are live musical performances designed for audiences of families with babies and young children. During these concerts, musicians already adapt their playing in response to the babies' visible behaviour, such as movement, attention and vocalisation. The Horizon Europe AMPLIFY project [2] aims to complement these visual observations with physiological signals, ultimately enabling babies to play a creative role via their measured physiological state. This pilot study uses adult participants to establish whether listeners exhibit measurable physiological changes in response to two contrasting musical excerpts from the 'Concertos para Bebés' album 'Amigos' [3], and whether those changes correlate with specific acoustic features. The findings are intended to refine the methodology and identify the most responsive physiological measures before subsequent evaluation with infant audiences. Prior research has demonstrated links between music listening and autonomic nervous system responses [4-6], but few studies have examined physiological responses at fine temporal resolution across multiple simultaneous listeners.

Section 2 reviews related work on music-evoked physiological responses. Section 3 describes our method, including details on the participants, the stimuli used and the analysis pipeline. Section 4 presents results of the study and is followed in Section 5 by a discussion of the findings. Conclusions and comments on the future direction of this research are presented in Section 6.

2 Related Work

The autonomic nervous system (ANS) mediates involuntary physiological processes, including heart rate, electrodermal activity and skin temperature, all of which can respond to musical stimulation [4-6]. For the 'Concertos para Bebés' use case, understanding which of these signals respond to specific musical characteristics, and with what temporal delay, is essential. Such information would allow musicians to incorporate real-time physiological data into their performances, complementing their existing visual observations of infant behaviour.

A foundational study by Bernardi et al. [4] continuously recorded cardiovascular and respiratory signals from 24 participants (12 musicians, 12 non-musicians) while they listened to excerpts of varying tempo. Faster tempi produced higher heart rates, increased respiration, and reduced baroreflex sensitivity, while musical pauses elicited relaxation responses comparable to silence. These findings established that tempo is a primary driver of cardiac ANS responses. A review by Koelsch [7] examined neuroimaging evidence showing that music activates limbic and paralimbic brain structures, including the amygdala and hippocampus, which mediate autonomic arousal and emotional processing. Using positron emission tomography and functional magnetic resonance imaging, Salimpoor et al. [5] showed that intensely pleasurable musical moments ('chills') trigger dopamine release in the caudate nucleus during anticipation and the nucleus accumbens during peak pleasure, providing a neurochemical basis for music-evoked ANS activation.

Electrodermal activity has also been studied as an objective marker of musical arousal. Craig [6] recorded skin conductance, heart rate and respiration from participants during self-selected music listening and found that 'chill' (frisson) episodes coincided with significant increases in skin conductance, confirming that discrete emotional peaks produce measurable phasic electrodermal responses. More recently, Chabin et al. [8] used high-density electroencephalography in a live concert setting with 13 participants to demonstrate inter-brain synchrony during pleasurable musical passages, suggesting that co-located listeners can exhibit shared physiological entrainment to musical features.

Despite these advances, few studies have used wearable sensors to simultaneously record multiple physiological modalities from co-located listeners, nor correlated physiological co-occurrences across individuals with specific acoustic features. The present study addresses these gaps by recording physiological data from groups of three co-located participants using EmotiBit™ wearable sensors during exposure to recorded musical pieces.

3 Method

The within-subjects repeated-measures study examined responses to two musical excerpts. Track presentation was counterbalanced to control for order effects.

3.1 Sample and Demographics

Convenience sampling yielded 33 participants recruited in groups of three. Three were lost to data corruption, giving $N = 30$ (20 male, 10 female; mean age 33, $SD = 11$, range 20-66). The sample included university students (9), academic staff (7), researchers (8), technicians (4) and other occupations (2). The majority (80%) reported no formal musical training.

3.2 Stimuli

For this pilot study, two musical excerpts were selected from the 'Concertos para Bebés' album "Amigos" [3] to preserve ecological validity within the Amplify project. Track 15 ('Concerto para Bebés - Exerto', ~2 min) is an instrumental jazz piece in 4/4 time at ~121 bpm, featuring prominent percussion alongside saxophone, clarinet and accordion, with disjointed staccato passages before the main melody. Track 18 ('Luna Lucente', ~2 min) is an arrangement

of Haydn's opera 'Il mondo della luna' in 2/4 time at ~100 bpm, featuring clarinet, saxophone, accordion and female operatic vocals over relaxed accompaniment. There are vocals in Track 18 whereas Track 15 features percussive elements. The tracks were chosen for their contrasting styles, tempos and instrumentation, their similar durations, and the use of instruments played by the 'Concertos para Bebés' musicians. Presentation order was counterbalanced. Audio was calibrated to 75 decibels of sound pressure level using Genelec 8010A studio monitors.

3.3 Audio Feature Extraction

Thirteen audio features were extracted at 10 ms resolution [9] using librosa [10]. The features, summarised in Table 1, span loudness, pitch, timbre, rhythm and spectral shape. MFCCs 1-3 are compact representations of timbre, modelling the nonlinear frequency resolution of human hearing [11].

3.4 Physiological Measures

Physiological data were recorded using EmotiBit™ wearable sensors. Table 2 summarises all firmware-recorded and software-derived measures. Heart rate, broadband electrodermal activity (EDA), skin conductance response (SCR) metrics, skin temperature and thermopile were recorded directly by the sensor. Inter-beat interval, heart rate variability (standard deviation of normal-to-normal (SDNN) and root mean square of successive differences (RMSSD)) and temperature rate of change were derived as listed. The undecomposed EDA signal, hereafter termed broadband EDA, contains both the slowly drifting tonic component (skin conductance level) and the rapid phasic component (event-related skin conductance responses) [17]. The EmotiBit™ firmware computes SCR amplitude, frequency and rise-time onboard using a threshold-based peak detector on the raw signal, without tonic/phasic decomposition. When sustained stimulation raises tonic skin conductance, these threshold crossings track slow drift rather than genuine phasic responses. We therefore used NeuroKit2 [13] to decompose the raw EDA into tonic and phasic components via cvxEDA [14], which models the tonic component as a cubic-spline baseline and recovers the phasic driver through constrained least-squares estimation. SCR peaks detected on the isolated phasic signal were used to derive SCR frequency (rolling 30 s count [17]), SCR amplitude and SCR rise-time. Validation confirmed firmware SCR frequency correlated with the tonic component (median $\rho = 0.43$, $p < 0.05$ in 88% of cases), whereas our software-derived features showed substantially weaker tonic association (median $\rho = 0.19$) and produced distinct correlations at shorter physiological lags. All subsequent analyses use these software-derived values.

3.5 Procedure

Participants were greeted in a sound engineering laboratory (Figure 1) and read an information sheet. Hearing was individually screened [15]. Participants attended in co-located groups of three. Each session ran identically. This consisted of a 5-minute resting baseline, the first excerpt (~2 min), a 2-minute recovery break where questionnaires relating to the first excerpt were administered (not analysed for this publication), the second excerpt (~2 min), and finally questionnaires were administered relating to the

Table 1: The 13 musical features identified from Track 15 and 18 of the ‘Concertos para Bebés’ ‘Amigos’ album.

Feature number	Feature Name	Characteristic
1-2	Amplitude, RMS Energy	Loudness
3	Fundamental Frequency	Pitch (high or low notes)
4	Spectral Centroid	Brightness (bright or dark sound)
5	Zero-Crossing Rate (ZCR)	Percussiveness / noisiness
6–8	MFCC 1, MFCC 2, MFCC 3	Timbre (tone colour)
9	Mean Chroma	Harmony (which notes are present)
10	Onset Strength	Rhythmic attack intensity
11	Spectral Bandwidth	Fullness of sound (full or thin)
12	Spectral Rolloff	Upper frequency limit
13	Spectral Flatness	Tonal clarity (noisy or clear)

Table 2: Physiological measures recorded and derived.

Category	Source	Measure	Description
Heart	EmotiBit firmware	Heart Rate (HR)	Beats per minute
	Derived	Inter-Beat Interval (IBI)	Time between successive heartbeats (ms): 60,000 / HR
		HRV – SDNN	Standard deviation of normal-to-normal IBIs: 300-sample rolling window [12]
		HRV – RMSSD	Root mean square of successive IBI differences: 300-sample rolling window [12]
Skin temperature	EmotiBit firmware	Temperature	Contact skin temperature sensor
	Derived	Thermopile	Non-contact infrared radiated body heat
		Temperature ROC	Instantaneous rate of temperature change: discrete first derivative
EDA	EmotiBit firmware	Broadband EDA	Undecomposed electrodermal activity (tonic + phasic)
	Derived	Tonic EDA	Slowly drifting skin conductance level: cvxEDA [14] via NeuroKit2 [13]
		Phasic EDA	Event-related skin conductance driver: cvxEDA [14] via NeuroKit2 [13]
		SCR Frequency	Rate of skin conductance responses: phasic peak detection (30 s rolling count [17])
		SCR Amplitude	Peak amplitude of each SCR: phasic peak detection
		SCR Rise-Time	Onset-to-peak duration of each SCR: phasic peak detection

second excerpt. Ambient lighting was reduced from ~1k lumens during onboarding to ~30 lumens during listening. Event timestamps were recorded via Lab Streaming Layer (LSL) for precise physiological-audio alignment. The acoustically treated studio provided a controlled temperature (24 °C) and lighting.

3.6 Data pre-processing

Standard threshold filters corresponding to normal physiological ranges removed movement artefacts. Heart rate values outside 30-220 bpm, EDA outside 0.01-100 μ S, skin temperature outside 25-42 °C, and IBI outside 200-270 ms were replaced with NaN. Artefact cleaning was applied to both baseline and stimulus periods before feature derivation, ensuring rolling-window statistics were not contaminated by outlier values (e.g., division by zero).

3.7 Analysis

Analysis followed five sequential steps as follows.

1 *Baseline* - Five minutes of pre-stimulus resting data were extracted.

2 *Individual deviation detection* - Each metric during each excerpt was compared to the participant’s baseline using Bonferroni-corrected Mann–Whitney U-tests, with effect sizes quantified as rank-biserial correlations as

$$r = 1 - 2U/(n_1n_2) \quad (1)$$

where r is the rank-biserial correlation coefficient, U is the Mann–Whitney U statistic, n_1 is the number of baseline time-point samples, and n_2 is the number of time-point samples for the same participant-track combination during the tracks.

3 *Common deviations* - Significant deviations shared (≥ 2) across participants in the same metric-track-direction combination were tabulated.

4 *Temporal co-occurrence detection* - Each participant’s time-series was detrended (30-second rolling median subtracted) then z-scored;

Figure 1: Onboarding and screening in the sound engineering control room.

contiguous windows where ≥ 2 participants simultaneously exceeded ± 2.0 SD [16] were identified as co-occurrence episodes.

5 *Episode-focused audio comparison* - Audio features during episodes were compared to the remainder of the track using Welch's t-test with Cohen's d (how big the difference was). The audio signal was shifted backward by 0-15 s in 1 s increments to account for physiological latency [4, 6, 13], retaining the best-fitting (peak effect) lag. Significance was Bonferroni-corrected across all tests.

4 Results

Results are presented across the following four subsections corresponding to the five analysis stages described in Section 3.7, with subsection 4.4 combining temporal co-occurrence of physiological deviations with audio changes.

4.1 Baseline Characterisation

Figure 2 presents baseline distributions for the three core EmotiBit™ metrics across all 30 participants. Heart rate and skin temperature exhibit concentrated, symmetric distributions centred on 72 BPM and 36 °C respectively. Electrodermal activity displayed expected inter-individual variability, spanning almost three orders of magnitude (0.03-17.8 μ S after outlier removal). This well-documented variation in tonic skin conductance [17] motivated our within-subject z-score normalisation.

4.2 Individual Deviations from Baseline

Table 3 shows statistically significant physiological deviations from baseline. A total of 489 Bonferroni-corrected ($\alpha = 0.05$) Mann-Whitney U-test deviations were detected across 30 participants and both tracks. Table 3 reveals a ceiling effect for slow-changing skin temperature and tonic EDA. Of 60 possible participant-track combinations, 57 produced significant deviations for both metrics, with near-total overlap (see Table 3, row 1 for Tonic EDA and row 5 for Temperature). This indicates both metrics captured a ubiquitous baseline shift. A plausible explanation is continued physiological acclimatisation during stimulus exposure despite the 5-minute pre-stimulus period. While statistically robust, these deviations may reflect environmental settling rather than stimulus-driven arousal and should be interpreted with caution. The faster-responding features phasic EDA and its SCR-derived metrics, as well as HRV, may be more plausible candidates for stimulus-specific responses.

4.3 Common Deviations

Table 4 presents common physiological deviations. These were significant baseline departures shared across multiple participants per metric, track and direction. Slow-responding features dominate with strong effect sizes.

Skin temperature increased in 25-27 of 30 participants on both tracks ($|r| = 0.876$ - 0.930) and tonic EDA increased in 18-22 participants ($|r| = 0.944$ - 0.969), likely reflecting continued environmental acclimatisation. More informative are the faster-responding features, which reveal track-differentiated and directionally heterogeneous patterns. Order-effect sensitivity checks (linear mixed-models) confirmed these track-differentiated responses were robust to presentation order. Parallel tests using the 2-minute break as a secondary baseline replicated 86% of the initial baseline deviations.

During Track 15, SCR frequency increased in 21 of 30 participants ($|r| = 0.694$), indicating a clear directional response to this excerpt. Track 18 produced a strikingly different pattern. SCR frequency was evenly split, with 14 participants showing a decrease and 14 an increase. No other metric exhibited this bidirectional split, suggesting that the phasic electrodermal response to Track 18 varied across listeners. Separately, phasic EDA showed a common decrease in 13 participants during Track 18, indicating reduced background electrodermal fluctuations even as discrete SCR events diverged in direction. Heart rate changes appeared only for Track 18, where 19 participants showed increased IBI (i.e. decreased heart rate), consistent with a parasympathetic (calming) response to that excerpt. These contrasting physiological patterns align with the musical differences between tracks. Track 18 is a classical operatic arrangement at a moderate tempo (*andante moderato*, ~ 100 bpm) with consonant harmonies, whereas Track 15 is a livelier jazz piece (*allegro*, ~ 121 bpm) with disjointed percussive passages and harmonic dissonance. We next examine whether changes in audio features during co-occurring physiological deviations differ from the remainder of the given track.

Figure 2: Distribution of raw physiological ratings at baseline.

Table 3: The statistically significant deviations from baseline of the physiological features (mean $|r|$ = mean absolute rank-biserial effect size).

Metric	Feature	<i>N</i> deviations	Mean $ r $	<i>p</i> (corrected)
EDA	EDA_tonic	57	0.931	0.000
	EDA_phasic	37	0.049	0.001
	SCR Frequency	56	0.681	0.000
Skin Temperature	Temperature	57	0.857	0.000
	Thermopile	56	0.902	0.000
Heart Rate	IBI_ms	38	0.454	0.003
	HRV_SDNN	15	0.231	0.000

Table 4: Common deviations across participants. Mean $|r|$ = mean absolute rank-biserial effect size.

Metric	Feature	Track	Direction	<i>N</i> participants	Mean $ r $	<i>p</i> (corrected)
Skin Temperature	Temperature	15	increase	27	0.884	0.000
	Thermopile		increase	25	0.930	0.000
	Temperature	18	increase	26	0.876	0.000
	Thermopile		increase	25	0.911	0.000
EDA	Tonic EDA	15	increase	18	0.969	0.000
	SCR Frequency		increase	21	0.694	0.000
	Tonic EDA	18	increase	22	0.944	0.000
	SCR Frequency		decrease	14	0.552	0.000
	SCR Frequency		increase	14	0.827	0.000
Heart Rate	IBI	18	increase	19	0.463	0.000

4.4 Episode-Focused Audio-Physiological Comparisons

To test whether shared physiological responses were linked to specific musical content, we compared audio features during co-occurring episodes to the remainder of each track. Audio features were shifted backward by 0-15 seconds to account for physiological latency [4, 6, 13], retaining the best-fitting lag. Effect sizes (Cohen’s *d*) and Welch’s *t*-tests were computed with Bonferroni correction across 80 metric-feature pairs with 27 surviving at $p < 0.05$. The full set is visualised in Figures 3 and 4 in the appendices, where each

row shows one metric-audio-feature pair as a time-aligned plot with co-occurrence episodes marked by coloured shading. Bars above each panel show episode timing and the number of simultaneous participants (*N*) with direction arrows (increasing or decreasing).

Track 15 produced the largest electrodermal effects (Figure 3). Nine broadband EDA episodes were associated with five audio features in two clusters. These were spectral brightness (rolloff $d = +1.48$, centroid $d = +1.47$, ZCR $d = +1.39$, all at lag 0 s) and timbral shape (MFCC1 $d = -1.44$, MFCC2 $d = -1.40$). Figure 3 shows the green episode shading is densest in the opening 40 seconds

where spectral rolloff and centroid peak simultaneously. A 0-2 s lag indicates essentially contemporaneous audio-electrodermal changes. Track 15 also yielded 5 heart rate episodes ($|d| = 0.95-1.45$), 6 temperature rate-of-change episodes ($|d| = 1.12-1.16$), and 3 tonic EDA episodes ($d = -1.24$).

The strongest cardiac results involved Track 18 (Figure 4, top five rows). IBI decreased ($d = -1.25$, lag +12 s) while heart rate increased ($d = +1.62$, lag +10 s) during rhythmically accented passages. This was a physiologically consistent pattern indicating cardiac acceleration ~10-12 seconds after strong rhythmic onsets. The episode shading for IBI and heart rate clusters in the first 70 seconds, aligning with the strongest rhythmic onsets. Heart rate episodes also showed elevated spectral centroid and fundamental frequency ($|d| = 0.55-0.66$), linking cardiac arousal to brighter, higher-pitched content.

Track 18 contributed two further electrodermal groups (Figure 4). Seven phasic EDA episodes were associated with onset strength ($d = +1.51$, lag +15 s) and four spectral features ($|d| = 0.64-0.79$, lag 6-8 s). Eight SCR frequency episodes showed elevated spectral rolloff and centroid ($|d| = 0.50-0.52$, lag +1 s). The phasic EDA episodes included two sustained periods, 1 at 56 s (5 participants) and 1 at 25 s (9 participants). Across both tracks, the 27 significant pairs span eight metrics. The dominant audio features are spectral brightness and timbral shape, with onset strength the primary cardiac and phasic EDA correlate.

Each co-occurrence episode, by definition, captures a moment when two or more participants deviated simultaneously. A separate question is whether the same individuals recur across episodes or whether different audience subsets are activated at different musical moments. To quantify this, we computed the mean pairwise Jaccard similarity (J) of participant sets across episodes within each metric ($J = 1$ identical membership; $J = 0$ no overlap) [18]. Heart rate exhibited very low overlap ($J = 0.10$ Track 15, $J = 0.16$ Track 18), with no participant appearing in every episode. Temperature rate-of-change showed the lowest overlap of all ($J = 0.07$), with completely disjoint participant sets across six episodes, and IBI drew from 17 unique participants across 12 episodes ($J = 0.17$). This turnover is a positive finding in that it indicates that the musical features elicited responses from different members of the audience at different moments, rather than repeatedly from a small hyper-responsive subset. By contrast, Track 15 broadband EDA was dominated by only 5 unique participants across 9 episodes, with 2 present in every episode ($J = 0.82$), reducing confidence that those associations generalise beyond those individuals. SCR frequency ($J = 0.41$) and phasic EDA ($J = 0.33$) fell between these extremes. Overall, the cardiac and temperature results carry the strongest external validity. The magnitude of the audio feature effect sizes ($d > 1$) during these distributed participant turnovers indicate that these small co-occurrences (~2 participants) reflect shared responses to the musical features rather than a random distribution which would regress to the track mean ($d \approx 0$) over the course of the ~2-minute track.

5 Discussion

This pilot study demonstrates the feasibility of using wearable physiological sensors to detect music-evoked responses. Two classes

of response emerged. These were the slow-drifting measures that shifted regardless of musical content, and faster-responding measures that differentiated between tracks and showed episode-level coupling with specific acoustic features. Skin temperature and tonic EDA fell into the first category, increasing in most participants with large effect sizes, likely reflecting environmental acclimatisation. Despite warranted concern that such slow-changing metrics might simply track environmental drift, careful handling such as baseline detrending, rate-of-change derivation for temperature, and tonic/phasic decomposition for EDA, allowed these signals to contribute meaningfully. Temperature rate-of-change and tonic EDA episodes correlated significantly with timbral features (MFCC1, MFCC2) at lags of 0-8 s (Figure 3), suggesting that slower autonomic channels respond to sustained musical passages rather than solely to sudden acoustic events.

The faster-responding phasic electrodermal measures proved more informative at the episode level. SCR frequency produced more co-occurrence episodes than any other metric across Track 15, with clusters of 5 and 9 simultaneous participants at distinct moments during the piece. The largest single episode (13 participants, 0-7 s) coincided with the track onset, where rising audio amplitude from silence may partly explain the synchronous EDA increase. However, the persistence of SCR-frequency co-occurrences well beyond the opening bars suggests it is a sensitive indicator of shared audience arousal to musical change. A methodological contribution is the identification and correction of tonic contamination in firmware-derived SCR metrics, with practical implications for researchers using wearable EDA sensors whose firmware outputs SCR metrics without decomposition.

Track 18 produced the clearest cardiac results. The longer lag compared to electrodermal responses is consistent with the slower parasympathetic withdrawal pathway [4, 19]. Heart rate episodes also showed elevated spectral centroid and fundamental frequency, linking cardiac arousal to brighter, higher-pitched content.

Limitations include the use of only two musical excerpts. Although differing in tempo and spectral brightness, both were from the 'Concertos para Bebés' repertoire to preserve ecological validity. This limits generalisability across broader genres. Subjective experience measures were not analysed alongside physiological data in this work-in-progress paper, precluding comparison between felt emotion and autonomic response. Musical style preferences and track familiarity were not collected but may bear on physiological responses.

6 Conclusion

This work presents a five-stage pipeline for analysing physiological responses to music using wearable sensors: baseline extraction, individual deviation detection, common deviation analysis, temporal co-occurrence detection and episode-focused audio comparison. From 489 significant individual deviations across 30 participants, 82 co-occurrence episodes were identified. Comparing audio features during these episodes yielded 27 Bonferroni-corrected significant pairs across eight physiological metrics (Figures 3 and 4 in Appendices A.1 and A.2 respectively). Electrodermal measures showed varied coupling latencies (0-2 s for broadband EDA and

SCR frequency; 6-15 s for phasic EDA), while cardiac measures operated at 0-12 s with the strongest effects at 10-12 s. SCR frequency emerged as the most collectively responsive metric, with episodes involving up to 13 simultaneous and 20 unique participants. Slower-responding measures such as skin temperature rate-of-change and tonic EDA, once properly detrended and decomposed, also revealed significant correlations with timbral features (MFCC1, MFCC2). A key methodological finding is that firmware-derived SCR metrics required software-based tonic/phasic decomposition to avoid contamination. The next stage of the AMPLIFY project will evaluate physiological responses of infants during both controlled and live 'Concertos para Bebés' performances.

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A APPENDICES

A.1 Track 15 – Bonferroni-significant physiological-music co-occurrences

Figure 3: Bonferroni-significant audio-physiological co-occurrence timelines for Track 15. Each row plots one audio feature (grey line) against the co-occurrence episodes of the associated physiological metric (coloured shading). Annotations above each episode indicate the number of simultaneously deviating participants and the direction of deviation (↑ elevated, ↓ reduced).

A.2 Track 18 – Bonferroni-significant physiological-music co-occurrences

Figure 4: Bonferroni-significant audio–physiological co-occurrence timelines for Track 18. Layout as in Figure 3. SCR frequency episodes span much of the track with the largest numbers of participants.